

**TURNING INFORMATION INTO A SOURCE OF INCOME
ПРЕВРАЩЕНИЕ ИНФОРМАЦИЮ В ИСТОЧНИК ДОХОДА
AXBOROTNI DAROMAD MANBAIGA AYLANTIRISH**

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Abstract: In today’s world, every action we do is related to information. We watch TV, read article, go to school or collage, communicate with people, discuss new topics, visit new places: all activities gives us specific type of information, it can be either experience or just knowledge. How to use this knowledge is up to us, the ones who can turn it into income source are winners.

Аннотация: В современном мире каждое наше действие связано с информацией. Мы смотрим телевизор, читаем статьи, ходим в школу или создаем коллаж, общаемся с людьми, обсуждаем новые темы, посещаем новые места: любая деятельность дает нам определенный тип информации, это может быть как опыт, так и просто знания. Как использовать эти знания, зависит от нас, победителями становятся те, кто сможет превратить их в источник дохода.

Annotatsiya: bugungi dunyoda biz qilayotgan har bir harakat axborot bilan bog'liq. Biz televizor ko'ramiz, maqolani o'qiymiz, maktabga yoki kollajga boramiz, odamlar bilan muloqot qilamiz, yangi mavzularni muhokama qilamiz, yangi joylarga tashrif buyuramiz: barcha tadbirlar bizga ma'lum turdagi ma'lumotlarni beradi, bu tajriba yoki shunchaki bilim bo'lishi mumkin. Ushbu bilimlardan qanday foydalanish bizga bog'liq, uni daromad manbaiga aylantira oladiganlar g'olibdir

Key words: eagerly seek out information, passive income, attract buyers, valuable information, investment, revenue streams, monetizing, valuable date, generate external revenue.

Ключевые слова: активный поиск информации, пассивный доход, привлечение покупателей, ценная информация, инвестиции, потоки доходов, монетизация, ценные данные, получение внешнего дохода.

Kalit so'zlar: ma'lumotni ishtiyiq bilan izlash, passiv daromad, xaridorlarni jalb qilish, qimmatli ma'lumotlar, investitsiyalar, daromad oqimlari, monetizatsiya, yaroqli muddat, tashqi daromad olish.

Turn Knowledge Into a 6-Figure Passive Income Stream with Online Courses
Selling the information

Turning data into software

In our world, information is incredibly valuable; without it, individuals and countries cannot progress. Information is an asset that can quickly guide you through the stages of development. If you look closely, the advancement in the West is largely due to their superior access to information. When it comes to the number of research articles published, the US and Europe lead, followed by Japan, China, and India.

This clearly shows that information is a powerful tool that can enable anyone to change their status rapidly. Think about how people **eagerly seek out information**. Many search the internet and YouTube for tools, while others look for ways to learn new skills daily. If you want to turn online courses into a source of **passive income**, you can be confident that they can provide a great return.

Before starting an online course, you need to decide which niche will **attract buyers**. While some courses can be quite expensive, it's not necessary to limit yourself to IT courses alone. Whether it's gardening, makeup, self-care, or cleaning, if you have **valuable information** in any field, you can deliver it effectively to others. So, definitely make an effort to create a video course related to your field.

Creating an online course doesn't require a significant **investment**; today's mobile devices are advanced enough to allow you to create videos. However, ensure that all your lectures are in simple language and easy to digest. Complex lectures can negatively impact your course sales, so aim for clarity. The explanation of the topic should be as clear as possible that everyone who is taking the course should understand everything easily. This is one of the keys of turning your knowledge into income.

If your course isn't on a highly specialized topic, keep the price reasonable. When people consider trying a new course, they often seek information about it first. A lower price can encourage them to try, while a high price may deter them.

Instruction: Keep your lectures concise in order not to confuse the audience so that they are going to pay for the course without hesitation. Try to include a quiz after every 15 minutes to help students retain key points. After each lecture, assign an assignment and verify the results; this will give the impression that students are genuinely learning in an institution.

It's also beneficial to involve two or more instructors in your course, as this enhances its credibility and makes it appear more professional. There are many platforms available where you can upload your course, but they typically take a commission when you make sales.

Creating an online course can be a profitable venture if you focus on a highly valuable niche. Use clear and simple language in your lectures and break complex topics into smaller, manageable subtopics to make the material easy to grasp. Pricing the course affordably can help attract more users. Including assignments after each section adds value for learners and can significantly boost your sales.

"In today's landscape, businesses are increasingly transforming their data and software into profitable products to enhance sales and explore new **revenue streams**. A 2023 survey by Deloitte revealed that over one-third (36%) of top executives acknowledge that their organizations are already generating income by selling data, technology, or tech-related services. Additionally, 16% plan to implement similar strategies within the next two years.⁹¹

Successfully achieving this requires significant operational changes, but the potential rewards can be substantial. Tech leaders should be at the forefront of this shift. For instance, the market for data monetization was valued at \$2.1 billion in 2020, with projections suggesting it could reach \$15.5 billion by the end of the decade, growing at an impressive annual rate of 22.1%. Despite recognizing the opportunities in **monetizing** data and technology, many tech leaders find their data management systems and capabilities remain basic".

While some organizations are making strides in data management, others may not yet be equipped to handle it effectively. Surprisingly, data management and analytics rank sixth among the top priorities for tech leaders, trailing behind digital strategy execution (1st), security, risk, and compliance (2nd), digital strategy development (3rd), innovation (4th), and operational reliability and delivery (5th).

The survey also highlights a lack of consensus on who is responsible for data management. About 35% of respondents believe that Chief Information Officers (CIOs) oversee data governance, while 34% think it's a shared responsibility between business and technology leaders. Additionally, 21% attribute it to collaboration among C-suite executives and tech leaders, and 8% assign it to non-IT executives. Two percent stated that there is no clear ownership of this task.

As organizations build their data infrastructure, tech leaders must actively plan for future **monetization opportunities** to avoid missing potential advantages.

With strong data management and governance practices in place, companies can start exploring strategies for monetization. While this process may present challenges, many organizations, regardless of their focus on technology, already hold **valuable data** that can be converted into **revenue streams**.

Organizations can leverage various types of data—including raw data, structured data, and insights from external sources—to create value in their operations and **generate external revenue**. The approach to data monetization will vary by company, but understanding the evolving rules and regulations governing data sharing is critical. Organizations must stay informed about these trends to navigate the data-sharing landscape responsibly; when in doubt, it's wise to refrain from sharing or selling data.

Effectively capitalizing on data monetization may also require making data more accessible across the organization. This often necessitates a coordinated effort

⁹¹ Deloitte "Global Data and Analytics Survey" (2023)

involving data platforms, fostering a data-centric culture, refining data processes, and ensuring effective communication and collaboration among stakeholders, including tech leaders, business leaders, data strategists, data owners, data scientists, and data stewards.

By developing a vision for leveraging data or technology to generate income, organizations can gain a competitive edge. Leaders across all industries have the opportunity to embark on this journey and unlock the potential of data monetization.

In exploring how to turn information into an income source, it's valuable to consider real-life examples. One individual's journey illustrates the potential of blogging about local news and building a community connection. His experience not only kept him engaged with his community but also enabled him to earn a daily income of \$100 from his blog. Below are the key strategies he employed to achieve this success, along with helpful hints for anyone looking to embark on a similar path.

Identifying the Niche

Small news is a (vertical in that phrase / non-wave feature), the audience being the residents of a specific area. Once I identified key areas of interest — they were local events, business news, community stories, and public announcements — I began by putting my finger on them. Customizing the content that I blog about, I knew immediately that it had a very specific charm.⁹²

Providing your audience with quality content is the main target of every performance-oriented blog. I made sure all my posts were based on proper research, correct and up-to-date to provide what I consider is the best information for my audience. Our content kept them coming back for updates being constant. Furthermore, I applied media tools to my posts by using photos, videos, and infographics to not only be more engaging but to also make them more attractive.

Imitation of community integration became my goal. I advertised my blog in both local Facebook groups and local notice boards as well as worked with some of the business owners. Through the events' hosting, contesting, as well as partnering with well-known influencers and local readership, the readership increased and thus loyalty was built.

Monetization Strategies: Several monetization strategies helped me achieve my daily income goal: Several monetization strategies helped me achieve my daily income goal:

Advertising: Besides that, I also indulged in selling advertising space to office companies that wanted to get to my audience. Another feature was Google AdSense which generated income based on number click and impression.

Social Media Promotion

⁹² Seth Together''This is marketing :You can not be seen until you learn to see''(2019)Penguin Random House

With reference to social media, I found it to be quite an effective advertising media for obviously my blog although. I started with creating and managing social media profiles on Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram, to publish my materials and interact with readers and readers. Real-time updates and interactive posts scores over in the business of social media by expanding it.

Analyzing Data and Adapting

Data gathering on a frequent basis including looking at the website traffic and engagement with readers displayed useful information of what posts were significant for the audience. I was wielding gauntlet Google Analytics to track performance and tweaking my content strategy in the light of the data gathered. Thus, it was thanks to the data-driven approach that I developed my blog step-by-step and got better and better.

Building Relationships: Strengthening ties with the community — business representatives, community leaders, and readers ensured success. I worked in teams, came up with stories, and used the stress of the people who live around me. Beyond the intellectual collaboration that improved the depth of the content, these relationships brought newest monetization and growth opportunities.

*Turning the presence of local news into a \$100 pregnancy by blogging can be successful with dedication, great content, and smart monetization. By crafting your blog thoughtfully around your community's needs, improving on SEO, blogging to engage readers, and diversifying your income sources, you could build a decent and solid local news blog. If you are a dreamer who wants to join journalism or are looking for an additional income which blogging about local news will give you, at the same time it will let you to get pleasure as well as find some money on this account.*⁹³

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⁹³ "Turning the presence of local news into a \$100 pregnancy by blogging"